

TYPES AND RESULTS OF DOCUMENT PROCESSING

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about documents, types of documents, document processing, types and features of document processing, library funds and their organization.

Keywords: document, book, information, library, interest, organization, result, fund, library fund.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada xujjat, xujjatlarning turlari, xujjatlarga ishlov berish, xujjatlarni ishlov berish turlari va xususiyatlari, kutubxona fondlari va ularni tashkil etish haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: xujjat, kitob, ma'lumot, kutubxona, qiziqish, tashkilot, natija, fond, kutubxona fondi.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о документах, видах документов, оформлении документов, видах и особенностях оформления документов, библиотечных фондах и их организации.

Ключевые слова: документ, книга, информация, библиотека, интерес, организация, результат, фонд, библиотечный фонд.

The librarian first takes into account the type, type and model of the library and tries to complete it with books. Stocking means acquiring and constantly updating books that match the reader's demand, interest, and the library's mission. Collection is the basis of the organization of the library fund, and the activity of the library begins with the acquisition of books. It is necessary to take into account the economic, cultural, and spiritual aspects of the area where this library is located, the composition, demand and interest of the population living there, what organizations and institutions exist in this place and complete information (card file) about their libraries. should be After that, sources of book acquisition are determined, contracts are concluded with them, and book acquisition is started. There are three types of idolization:

- 1). Current batch - get published and in-progress books.
- 2). Retrospective - retrieval of previously published books.
- 3). Removal from the stock - removal of old, torn books.[1]

The most important of them is the current collection, in which 80-90 percent of the books are taken, and the missing books are taken in the retrospective collection. How much and how much this fund will be depends on the type of library. Building the library fund consists of four stages.

Stage 1. Bibliographic manuals reporting on published documents are considered. Bibliographic guides include: thematic plans of publishers, bulletins of book trade institutions, bibliographic parts of newspapers and magazines, various bibliographic indices. After carefully examining these publications, an order is made to a collector or a bookstore to obtain the relevant books. "Newspaper and magazine catalogs" are used to obtain periodicals. In order to control the arrival of ordered documents, a current order file is created.

Stage 2. Initial selection. After determining the source of the book, the selection of books will proceed. It consists of five stages:

1). Depending on the formal designation of the books, they are selected from bibliographic manuals according to whether they correspond to the fund or not.

2). This stage is very complicated and difficult, and it is selected based on the content, field, and readability of the book. For this, a librarian must be qualified, knowledgeable, able to understand many fields, and be able to do logical analysis. Only then can the library choose relevant, educational, meaningful and interesting books for the library. When choosing a book, the librarian carefully examines the subject plans of the publishers, examines the book's author, title, and abstract, and focuses on whom it is intended for. When choosing books in a foreign language, books with fundamental knowledge necessary for specialists are selected, taking into account the currency and language. A librarian may not be well versed in all fields of science, so it is often better to involve specialists in a certain field, subject in the selection of books. Large libraries use experts from different fields in the selection, so that unnecessary books are reduced in the fund.[2]

3). It is determined whether the selected documents will come in internal or external structures. Before ordering a book, the buyer should know whether this book is available in the collection, how much it is in other neighboring libraries, and how it is being read. After that, this book will give an order if it is needed, if it is not needed, it will not order it.

4). Funds given to the library are taken into account. Firstly, spending the given funds on unnecessary books does not benefit either the state or the reader, and secondly, the lack of funds for the necessary books worsens the service and causes the reader to leave the library. Exchange funds, depository libraries appear. it has been. The inter-library subscription was not completed, book exchange was non-existent. Books have become more expensive now. it is necessary to establish internal and external book exchange and to remove obstacles that hinder it.

5). Making a conclusion from the above, based on the initial selection, the bottling begins. The current batch will continue.

Stage 3. Ordering documents. Sources, ways and forms of obtaining documents. The sources, ways, and methods of replenishing the library fund differ from each other. [3]

A source is an entity from which a book is obtained, which can be an organization, an institution, or an individual. Libraries received 80 percent of books from library collectors. The library signs a contract with the collector, in which it undertakes to provide the books and finance them for one year. The collector, in turn, undertakes to provide the library with the ordered books. They also buy from bookstores. It is easy and convenient to get books from stores, because the books arrive at the library on time. One of the ways to increase the efficiency of the library fund is exchange of books between libraries. For large national and scientific libraries, a system of mandatory paid and free copies has been introduced. Mandatory copies are sent by the state to large national and regional libraries. Depending on their scale, they can be national and local, paid and free depending on their direction, general or for any purpose depending on the field. stands Through such a system, designated libraries receive all the publications issued in a certain place and save them and deliver them to the reader. Compulsory copying was introduced in 1537 by the King of France, Francis I, who decided to send a certain copy of the book published by all publishers for his personal library.[4]

At the same time, he replenished the stock of the world's largest libraries and enriched them with rare books. Free compulsory copying libraries receive all types of press works, documents in all languages. Compulsory paid copying was introduced in 1931, and it is mainly used by the system of scientific libraries. Its purpose is to provide scientific libraries with the necessary literature. The most common way to supply these libraries with documents is to pre-order published books.

Step 4. Acceptance of newly arrived books. Complete and timely arrival of the ordered books from the sources of book acquisition is monitored. The librarian checks and compares all the documents related to the books coming to the library with the received books. If the name, quantity, and price of the books they ordered have changed, the reader can cancel them if they don't need them. For the books that were not ordered or are not listed in the documents, a deed will be drawn up and sent back to the accounting department. The rest of the books are given a conditional mark and handed over to the library fund.

Everything in the world is calculated. That is why, as in every field, the publications that come and go in libraries are taken into account. Because accounting is information.

Information about the fund is widely used in the activities of libraries, because the basis of the organization of the fund is accounting, and the library is controlled on this basis. The following requirements are set when accounting for the fund:

- Accurate and complete information about the fund.
- Documentation of publications received and issued from the library.
- Timely and quick registration of publications.
- Consistency of accounting results with information about received books.

There are two types of accounting in the library.[5]

General accounting. With the help of general accounting, accurate information about the composition and size of the fund is collected. All publications received or issued from the library are included in the general account. Collective data is reflected in the "Library fund accounting book", which consists of three parts.

- 1). Copies presented to the fund.
- 2). Copies issued.
- 3). End of fund movement.[6]

Annual, daily and other forms of accounting have been integrated to make the library statistics uniform. The compatibility of all parts and sections of the general calculation facilitates the calculation and provides an opportunity to obtain information about the entire fund or any part of it. In large libraries, in addition to the general book for the entire fund, they keep a special book for each individual fund. Branches will have an inventory book.

Single account. Individual registration means separate registration of each copy of the publication received or issued from the fund. Timely press and audiovisual materials are taken into account in the same order. Each copy of the book taken to the library is assigned a separate inventory number. Libraries receive a variety of materials according to their type and type, so in order to take into account especially periodicals, books, serials, these publications are represented as a unit (or roof) that fits the association. Each typographically independent press work is called a printed unit: book, brochure, reprint of books, separate issue of a magazine, poster, sheet music, standard, etc. In order to unify the account for such types of publications, accounting of the document according to the publication number has been introduced in accordance with international requirements. In such cases, each individual publication is

considered for the unit of account. This account provides detailed information about each publication in the fund. Scientific libraries count the number of periodicals as a unit of account. Also, a box, folder, disk, cassette, cuff, set (diopositive, slide), etc. can serve as a unit of account. Such variety has a negative effect on accounting.

Therefore, researches have been conducted and are being conducted to find a single unit in the world. For example, the filled racks are metered (for books, brochures, periodicals, manuscripts), rolls (for information on tapes), physical units (for flat microfilms), etc. accounting is carried out in catalogs and card files, registration books, etc. The inventory book is the main form of accounting.

The inventory number of the books taken from other libraries to the depository fund is marked "D". When the stock is checked, the librarian receives it through the inventory book when it is exchanged, because it is an important document. Libraries with large holdings use a single account filing system to speed up inventory. In this system, a list of documents is created for each group of books received in the library, which provides an opportunity to complete the calculation.[7]

The basic information about the book is also written in these documents and starts from No. 1 every year. The document number that each book will have usually consists of three elements. Year of registration, document number and serial number of the book list in it: 1992-16 (126). At the end of the year, all documents are collected and made into a book like an inventory book. Forms that allow for simple, accurate, quick accounting are being sought and some are being used. For example, if a book is purchased in multiple copies, only the name of the publication is written and the number of copies is indicated in the inventory book or card, without recording each copy as before. Several (3-5) copies of textbooks received in the libraries of higher educational institutions are recorded in the inventory book, and the rest are included in the account with the word "without inventory". the number of issued and remaining copies, the code of the textbook recorded in the inventory book is shown. Card files are created from the account card to the fund of educational literature.

Each card has a sequential number in a special record book. The same information as in the usual inventory book is transferred to this book, only the number of the account card is entered in the column of the inventory number and the number of copies is indicated. In technical libraries, a non-inventory accounting sheet is used for normative technical documents (standard numbers,

publications, etc.). Their number is taken into account in the catalogs. Literature issued from the fund is issued by a document.

The reasons for issuance are indicated in each document: torn, outdated, multiple copies, not appropriate to the field. A list of books to be issued after the document is drawn up is attached. After the decision is approved by the leaders of the higher organization, it is determined in the individual account documents that the publication is withdrawn from the fund. In the general accounting book, it is noted that this batch of books has been written off. Their cards are removed from the catalog. From these cards, alphabetical cards of the account are made and the calculation is carried out in this way.

Checking the library funding. The check is to compare the fund with individual accounting documents and determine the existence of registered publications. Control is the control of accounting.

The following can be determined by inspection:

- Has the library taken into account all the books or not?
- Books that can be repaired, covered, re-encrypted.
- Order of placing books on the shelves.
- Giving books to readers and following the deadline for returning them, indebted readers, reading level of books, etc.
- Accounts for the fund, processing and identifies responsible persons who made mistakes.

Inspection is carried out in the following cases:

- when planned;
- when the head of a department or branch changes in the library;
- in case of fire, natural disaster;
- it is carried out when the accounting is found to be unsatisfactory.

Planned inspection is carried out in 7-10 years or in the period determined by the higher organization.

Check methods:

- inventory book;
- registration directory, registration directory;
- special equipment: control cards, index card, topographic catalog, etc.

Inspection methods depend on the conditions of the library, the size of the fund, the method of placement, and the accounting form used. For example, when the fund is arranged in the inventory format, it is easy to check through the inventory book, but if the fund is arranged systematically, this procedure is not correct or it is difficult to check.

Libraries with a large fund create a topographic catalog, they use it for inspection. The inspection of control cards is widely popular, and during the inspection, a separate card is written for each book, on which: inventory number, password, author's last name, first name, and the first word of the title are written. Under the password, it is indicated in which section of the library the book is, if the book is on hand, the information is obtained from the reader's formulas.

Checking method: checked books are stamped with the date checked. Then the cards written in the book are placed in increasing order of numbers and compared with the inventory book, and a conditional mark is placed in the check column. determines the reason for its absence. If the book is not found, a list of them is drawn up and attached to the certificate of inspection. When the inspection is completed, the inspection slips are not thrown away, but are filled with the slips of newly received books, and the slips of the books issued from the fund are removed and used in the next inspection. Accounting and checking of the library fund is of great importance. On the basis of the accounting documents, the fund is kept, its transfer from one employee to another, and the annual statistical report is controlled. The librarian should compare the received literature with the application document, seal it and record it in the accounting documents of the library. There are two types of accounting of literature: general "Library fund general accounting book" and individual "Individual accounting book" types.

"The general ledger of the library fund" consists of 3 parts. In the first part, the entry of the book into the fund, in the second part, the withdrawal from the fund, and in the third part, the results of the movement of the fund are taken into account. It is mandatory for every library to keep a "general account book of the library fund". The individual account of the library fund is recorded in the "Individual account book". "Individual account book" is a very important document of the library, which should be handled with extreme care and caution. As soon as the book arrives at the library, it is processed and formalized, and a seal is printed on the title page and page 17. After that, it is recorded in the individual account book. The work of processing the book is not limited to this: it is necessary to divide it into sections, assign it to catalog cards, put a book form (password, individual account number, author's name, name and price of the book).

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